

Deliverable 9.1

Data Management Protocol

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Table of Contents

1. Introduction	4
2. Ethical and Legal Framework	5
2.1. General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).....	5
2.2. Additional Local Legislation of countries involved within FIT4FOOD2030	6
3. Data Summary.....	9
3.1. Types of Data	9
3.2. Purpose of data collection and relation to the objectives of the project.....	10
4. Data storage and security	22
4.1. Data storage and security	22
4.2. Transfer of personal data.....	23
4.3. Data recovery.....	25
5. FAIR Data.....	26
5.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	26
5.2. Making data open accessible	26
5.4. Increase data re-use.....	27
6. Allocation of resources	28
6.1. Costs for making data FAIR and for long term preservation	28
6.2. Responsibilities for data management	28
7. Ethical aspects.....	28
Appendix 1. Template Horizon 2020 DMP	30
Appendix 2. Publication Plan	32
Appendix 3. Sample Informed Consent Form Training and Learning Sessions	33
Appendix 4. Sample Media Release Form Training and Learning sessions	34

1. Introduction

FIT4FOOD2030 has been established to support the European Commission (EC) in further development and implementation of the FOOD 2030 policy framework and its action plan. This Coordination and Support Action (CSA) aims to establish a sustainable multi-stakeholder, multi-level platform, mobilizing a wide variety of stakeholders at the level of cities, regions, countries, and Europe; the FOOD 2030 Platform. The project will support the urgently needed transformation of research and innovation (R&I) on food and nutrition security (FNS) by providing a network and instruments for the adoption of a food system and Responsible Research and Innovation (RR&I) approach to R&I.

Over the course of the project several types of data will be generated. Adequate protection and exploitation of data and results in the various work packages (WPs) of the project receive high priority. The Data Management Protocol (DMP; present document) aims to provide an overview of principles and guidance of the main elements of the data management policy that will be used by the consortium partners with regard to all data that will be generated. Furthermore, the DMP includes how to communicate results in an ethical and transparent way. However, this DMP does not replace any of the established agreements, including the Consortium Agreement (CA), the Grant Agreement (GA) and the Annotated Model Grant Agreement, nor does it replace any of the EU guidelines for project implementation and documentation. In particular, the CA functions as a central document on data management matters, stating the rights and obligations of all beneficiaries related to the following issues: dissemination of project results and data; ownership of results; protection of results; and access rights.

The DMP is mainly structured according to the template of Horizon 2020 about DMPs (Appendix 1). This DMP starts with a legal framework, including the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and how this relates to the different European countries involved within the consortium, is described first. Subsequently, Chapter 2 includes the three types of data which are defined within the project, as well as a summary of data collected per WP. Chapter 3 describes data storage and data security. In Chapter 4 more detail is provided on how the project relates to the four "FAIR" principles: findable, accessible, interoperable, and re-usable. Chapter 5 describes the allocation of resources. Finally, Chapter 6 describes any ethical and legal issues related to data collecting and data sharing.

The DMP is a living document and is expected to evolve with the project. The DMP will be updated accordingly by the Project Management Team of the Coordinator (VU) and presented to the Executive Board (EB).

2. Ethical and Legal Framework

The consortium of FIT4FOOD2030 includes partners from different European countries, including the Netherlands, Norway, Austria, Spain, Belgium, France and Italy. Furthermore, Policy and City Labs of FIT4FOOD2030 are located in the following additional countries: Bulgaria, Estonia, Greece, Hungary, Lithuania and Romania (table 1).

Given this broad spectrum of countries, the consortium is well aware of the international legislation, guides and codes that regulate management of data:

- The Nuremberg Code (1947) addressing volunteer consent and proper acting;
- The Revised Declaration of Helsinki in its last version of 2013;
- The General Data Protection Regulation (2018, see below);
- Opinions of the European Group of Advisers on the Ethical Implications of Biotechnology (1991-1997) and the European Group on Ethics in Science and New Technologies (as from 1998);
- The New Brunswick Declaration: A Declaration on Research Ethics, Integrity and Governance resulting from the 1st Ethics Rupture Summit, Fredericton, New Brunswick, Canada (2013);
- The Respect Code focused in socio-economic research.

Table 1. Countries involved within FIT4FOOD2030

Country	Consortium/City Lab/Policy Lab
The Netherlands	Consortium and City Lab and Policy Lab
Norway	Consortium and Policy Lab
Austria	Consortium
Spain	Consortium and City Lab
Belgium	Consortium and Policy Lab (Flanders)
France	Consortium
Italy	Consortium and City Lab and Policy Lab
Bulgaria	City Lab
Estonia	City Lab
Greece	City Lab
Hungary	City Lab and Policy Lab
Lithuania	Policy Lab
Romania	Policy Lab

2.1. General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)

At this moment, European countries have their own national legislation regarding personal data protection, based on the European Data Protection Directive 95/46/EC (1995).

However, from 25 May 2018, the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) will be enforced and will replace the Data Protection Directive 95/46/EC. The aim of the GDPR is “to allow EU citizens to better control their personal data”. It is a **single set of EU-wide rules applicable** to all countries within the European Economic Area (EU, and Norway, Liechtenstein and Iceland), and as such all countries involved within the FIT4FOOD2030-project.

Although the GDPR is applicable to all countries, the GDPR multiple references to the rights of Member States, allowing them to maintain or introduce national specificities. Therefore, several countries will have additional local legislation of which the consortium needs to be aware of. However, most countries will have a draft legislation at this moment in time. This means, this section should be updated after 25 May 2018.

2.2. Additional Local Legislation of countries involved within FIT4FOOD2030

The Netherlands

From 25 May 2018 the “Algemene Verordening Gegevensbescherming” (AVG) will most probably be enforced by the Dutch Data Protection Authority (“Autoriteit Persoonsgegevens”). The AVG is the implementation law of the GDPR and replaces the Dutch Personal Data Protection Act (‘Wbp’). At this moment the AVG needs official approval from the Senate of the Dutch Parliament. Detailed information on the AVG can be found on the website of the [Dutch Data Protection Authority](#).

Norway

Norway has drafted a proposal for a new national data protection legislation that will incorporate the GDPR. However, as the proposal has not yet been presented to the Norwegian Parliament for approval, the implementation may be slightly delayed. It is expected that the new legislation will mainly implement GDPR without significant changes.

Austria

From 25 May 2018 a law amending the national data protection act (“Datenschutzgesetz”) will come into effect in order to implement the GDPR at national level. An English translation of the Austrian Data Protection Act can be found within the [electronic law system of Austria](#) (“RIS”).

As of now Austria made no use of the possibility to make use of the derogations from the rights of data subjects stipulated within Art 89 GDPR. On the contrary, Sec 7 and 8 of the Austrian Data Protection Act govern the rightful use of personal data for scientific research purposes on a more detailed level than the GDPR.

In order to establish a balance between the fundamental right for privacy and scientific freedom, yet additional rules are being discussed by the Austrian Parliament. An amendment of the “Forschungsorganisationsgesetz” could implement rules for the use of personal data for scientific purposes and make use of the derogations within Art 89 GDPR. German information about the political proceeding can be found on the website of the [Austrian Parliament](#). As of now it is unclear whether the law will be enacted by the parliament.

Spain

The Spanish regulation concerning data protection is composed by “[Ley Orgánica 15/1999, de 13 de diciembre, de Protección de Datos de Carácter Personal](#)” and the specific regulation about its [implementation](#). After the approval of the new EU regulation (GDPR) some modifications to the current regulations are required. For this reason, the Spanish legislation will be updated in order to be aligned with the European one.

Belgium

The Belgian law [C – 2017/31916] establishes the creation of the Belgian Data Protection Authority (“Autorité de protection des données”/“Gegevensbeschermingsautoriteit”), responsible for the implementation of the GDPR. The Data Protection Authority will be functional on 25 May, replacing the current Commission for the Protection of Privacy (“Commission vie privée”/“Privacycommissie”). The legal document can be found in this [link](#). More information (in Dutch) can be found [here](#).

France

The following paragraph is extracted from the website of [Ashust law firm](#): “On 17 December 2017, the Government opted to amend and not repeal and replace the Act of 1978 by adopting a Bill of law insuring the adaptation of national legislation to the European right for the protection of personal data. Once the law is adopted, the Government will then have 6 months to ensure the implementation of the GDPR through a final Order that will ensure its practical efficiency.

As a result, so far, the French Data Protection Act of 1978, in its revised version, will remain applicable after 25 May 2018 and will need to be read concurrently with the GDPR”.

Italy

The Italian law related to the protection, use and spreading of personal data is included in the “[Codice in materia di protezione dei dati personali](#)” (D.lgs 196/2003). After the approval of the new UE Regulation of GDPR in May 2018, the Italian law will be updated accordingly in order to align the Italian legislation to the European one.

Bulgaria

The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) will be enforced in Bulgaria from 25 May 2018. Additions and amendments to the Personal Data Protection Act have been prepared and after public consultation the texts will be submitted to the Legal Commission of the National Assembly. More information can be found on the [Bulgarian Commission for Personal Data Protection site](#).

Estonia

Starting from 25 May 2018, the European General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) will be enforced in Estonia. It will be accompanied by the Estonian Personal Data Protection Act ([Isikuandmete kaitse seadus](#)).

Greece

In Greece the [Hellenic Data Protection Authority](#) is active. More specifically, the Law 2472/1997 Protection of Individuals with regard to the Processing of Personal Data (and 3471/2006 Protection of personal data and privacy in the electronic telecommunications sector and amendment of law 2472/1997) protects citizens' rights vis-a-vis those who keep and process their personal data (Data Controllers). These rights are the following: the right to information, the right to access and the right to object.

Specifically, regarding data collection from students, in Greece, the Institute of Educational Policy is the legal entity that is responsible for any activities in Greek schools. All schools need to obtain permission from IEP in order to participate in any projects. The Institute of Educational Policy (IEP) was established in 2011 under Public Law 3966. It is a private legal entity supervised by the Minister of Education Research and Religious Affairs. IEP operates for the benefit of public interest as an executive scientific body that supports the Ministry of Education and Religious Affairs on issues relating to primary and secondary education and the transition from secondary to higher education. IEP's primary mission is the scientific research and study of issues related to all levels of education, the continuous technical support for the design and implementation of educational policy issues and the implementation of ESF and ERDF co-funded projects in the framework of ESPA 2013- 2020. For the collection of data by students (or video recordings in the classroom) consent forms are needed.

Hungary

Hungary protects the personal data with a high regulatory background. The [Fundamental Law of Hungary](#) (2011) defines the right to personal data as a constitutional fundamental right (Article VI., (2) and (3)). From 28 May onwards the GDPR will be used like a Hungarian law.

Lithuania

Requirements for the protection of personal data is established in the Article 12 of The Law on Legal Protection of Personal Data of the Republic of Lithuania (No. I-1374 of 11 June 1996) regulating the protection of an individual's right to privacy regarding the processing of personal data in Lithuania.

This Law establishes the rights of natural persons as data subjects, the procedure for the protection of these rights, the rights, duties and responsibility of legal and natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data.

Under the Law:

- Carrying the scientific research, personal data must be processed if the data subject has given his consent. Without the consent of the data subject personal data for research purposes can be processed only after notification to the State Data Protection Inspectorate. In this case, the State Data Protection Inspectorate must carry out a prior check.
- The personal data used for the scientific research must be replaced so that the identity of the data subject cannot be determined.
- For the scientific research collected and stored personal data cannot be used for other purposes.

Currently, there is no additional information available regarding potential additional legislation next to the GDPR. At the university a specific policy regarding security of personnel data will be established soon.

Romania

Regarding data management legislation, there is no specific additional local legislation in Romania but the EU regulation will have to be applied ad literam from May 25.

3. Data Summary

3.1. Types of Data

In relation to personal data and measures to protect it, CA of FIT4FOOD2030 has specified three types of data (article 1.2).

- **Personal Data:** “any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person. An identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one of more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural, or social identity of that natural person”.
- **Research Data:** “retrospective and prospective clinical, pre-clinical, genetic, longitudinal, follow-up and other information (including but not limited to numerical scores, textual records, images and sounds) about individuals, generated or made available pursuant to the Grant Agreement and/or this Consortium Agreement, and excluding Stakeholder Data”.
- **Stakeholder Data:** “information (including but not limited to numerical scores, textual records, images and sounds) about individuals employed by or otherwise linked to a stakeholder and generated or made available by a party pursuant to the project”.

To add to the above definition, stakeholder data refer to data containing personal identifiers (e.g. name, organization and email address) of contact persons of organisations that are related or linked to the concept or activities of the FIT4FOOD2030 project in various ways. More specifically, people who represent their organisations and/or participate project activities in their professional capacity, can be regarded as stakeholders. This would cover, for example, contact persons of stakeholders participating the City and Policy Lab events or those who are part of their transformative networks. As a consequence, minutes and reports of these activities might contain stakeholder data (i.e. the names, etc.), unless those persons specifically chose otherwise.

Another important example where stakeholder data can be found is the stakeholder database (collaboratively developed by WP1, WP7 and WP8). Stakeholder data in this database includes *organization, organization’s website, e-mail address, gender, “stakeholder category”* (NGO/CSO, Business, Policy makers, Knowledge and education centres, Funding agencies, Other), and finally, *“area of activity”* (Agriculture, Aquaculture, Health, Environment, Other). This information will be collected via the stakeholder registration form (Excel sheet), developed by HiOA (WP8) and can be sent to EUFIC (WP7). Stakeholders collected via this registration form will be contacted by email to ask if they would like to be in the stakeholder database, and if so, in what way they would like to be involved within the FIT4FOOD2030-project. The exact procedure is currently under development. Based on stakeholders’ answers to the questions in this email, consortium partners are allowed to contact those stakeholders who decided to be involved in the project.

Examples to research data include, data collected via surveys, interviews, focus group discussions and other quantitative and qualitative methods, EXCLUDING the stakeholder data. For example, the data collected via the surveys involving WP2, WP3 and WP4 is research data by definition. Nevertheless, at the end of the survey, the participants may want to sign up to the stakeholder database, to be informed about the developments about the project (independent from the data they provided at the survey). In that case, they also become the stakeholders and the data they provide (their names, organisation, contact information, etc.) become stakeholder data. This stakeholder data can be transferred among partners. However, it should be noted that their

responses to the survey or their responses to the interview questions can only be transferred in pseudonymized form.

Also, there might be cases that research participants of an interview wish to remove the obligation for keeping their personal data confidential partially or completely. In that case, depending on the purpose of the activity, some personal identifiers (such as name & organisation) can be stated in external publications, provided that these participants give explicit consent for it. When considering to name organizations or individual people in reports which will be open to public, it is important to consider the need to do it from a technical perspective in order to guarantee research quality.

For the data collected during meetings or activities within the consortium and/or the FOOD 2030 platform (EU Think Tank, Policy Lab and City Lab coordinators) – e.g. data generated during the lab coordinator trainings or data generated during the Dynamic Learning Agenda intervention sessions – there is no need to pseudonymize the data before it is transferred to the relevant partners. An Edugroepen sub-page has been developed to store and transfer data from the Lab coordinator trainings (only accessible for VU, HiAO, AIT) and the DLA intervention sessions (only accessible for VU, HiAO, Ecsite).

At this moment, it is not possible to identify every possible case that may be faced during the course of the project. Decisions on what activities produce which kind of data can also be made in a deliberative process as and when needed. Final decisions will be made by the respective partner/ WP leader after the issue is discussed with the Coordinator. To facilitate the process, the Coordinator may consult the legal advisors and data management officers at VU. If an agreement is not reached with the relevant partner/ WP leader and the Coordinator, or if deemed necessary, the issue might be taken to the Executive Board for a decision.

All updated versions of this deliverable will be shared with and communicated to the Consortium via Edugroepen and email.

3.2. Purpose of data collection and relation to the objectives of the project

In this project, data will be collected to achieve the following objectives:

1. To develop three interlinked structures with appropriate instruments, namely:
 - An **'EU Think Tank'** that acts as a linking pin between the EC and MS/AC; and will have a global outreach.
 - **'Policy Labs'** that mobilize stakeholders in order to align R&I policies and investment schemes, integrating existing networks of FNS related JPIs, ETPs, KICs and SMART Specialization Platforms, expanded with stakeholders not yet strongly linked to the FOOD 2030 dialogues, such as Civil Society Organizations (CSOs), consumers (users) and citizens;
 - **'City Labs'** that develop and pilot hands-on (in)formal trainings for students and professionals by linking Science Centres and Museums, and Science Shops to the networks of the cities of the Milan Urban Food Policy Pact (MUFPP), bringing a wide diversity of actors together.
2. To acquire insights into food system trends and related R&I policy frameworks, best practices (showcases) and future R&I breakthroughs;
3. To execute effective and targeted communication and dissemination activities adapted to different stakeholders, as well as develop a plan for continued communication beyond the project, thereby maximising the outreach and impact of FIT4FOOD2030's outputs and policy recommendations.

4. To carry out scientific studies that yield reports and publications. This is important to contribute to the scientific literature with the experiences and findings of the project.

To provide clarity on the connections between objectives and data collection, and to provide more detail on the characteristics of the data generated, this section is divided in the different WPs and its tasks if possible. Tables below outline the types of data connected to each WP task, and whether quantitative (QT) and/or qualitative (QL) methods will be used or whether secondary data will be used. Furthermore, it outlines data utility, type of data and data size.

According to the information risk classifications of the VU, all data generated within FIT4FOOD2030 will be of **low or moderate risk**¹. High risk data refers to strictly confidential information (e.g. patient records, passwords, and credit card numbers) or high risk research (e.g. biomedical research, high risk chemical experiments) which is not the case within FIT4FOOD2030.

In addition to the description of tasks and deliverables presented at the Grant Agreement, Description of Action, Part A, the consortium plans to make additional publications in the form of scientific articles. A 'publication plan' is currently being prepared by each WP leader to list the planned scientific articles that will be produced within the project (Appendix 1). This plan might identify other or additional data that needs to be collected. Therefore, based on the publication plans of WPs, the below tables may be updated. The publication plan itself will also be updated every year and these will be reflected to the below tables of the DMP.

¹ *Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam Information Risk Classifications (Nov. 2017).*

Document name: 171101_InformationSecurity_Confidentially Matrix (available upon request)

Table 1. Overview of the characteristics of data collected/used for WP1 (VU) - Methodology to build the FOOD2030 Platform

Task	Title Task	Responsible Partner(s)	Outputs (month, type, dissemination level)	Dataset Description & Collection Methods (QL/QT)	Data Utility (objective)	Type of Data & Data Format
T1.1 (M1-36)	Design and instigate an approach for a transformative network	VU	D1.1 (M4, Report, Public) MS6 (M4): Training session #1 (M4)	Notes and minutes, training recordings and transcriptions, photos (QL)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ To learn and monitor; ○ To investigate and understand the evolution of the transformative network 	Word files (DOCX), Audio files (MP3/MP4), Image files (JPEG)
T1.2 (M1-10)	Develop a methodology for identifying relevant stakeholders	HiOA	D1.2 (M4, Database, Confidential)	Stakeholder data (including stakeholders from all over world), by means of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ A questionnaire for partners of the Consortium (Kick Off); ○ An “excel registration form” to be filled in by consortium and Policy and City Labs (QL) ○ Other methods to be determined 	To track the growing network over time	Excel file (XLSX)
T1.3 (M1-3)	Adapting methodologies for multi-stakeholder dialogues in phase 1	AIT	-	-	-	-
T1.4 (M6-12)	Adapting methodologies for identifying showcases and pathways to R&I breakthroughs	VU	D1.3 (M6, Report, Public) MS12: Training session #2 (M7 and M13)	Notes and minutes of training, training recordings and transcriptions, photos of training (QL)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ To learn and monitor; ○ To investigate and understand the evolution of the transformative network 	Word files (DOCX), Audio files (MP3/MP4), Image files (JPEG)
T1.5 (M10-36)	Adaptation of methods and tools to guide action planning and training in labs	VU	D1.4 (M16, Report, Confidential) MS17: Training session #3 (M16)	Notes and minutes, training recordings and transcriptions, photos (QL)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ To learn and monitor; ○ To investigate and understand the evolution of the transformative network 	Word files (DOCX), Audio files (MP3/MP4), Image files (JPEG)
T1.6 (M1-36)	Connecting the CoPs of the FOOD2030 Platform	VU	D1.5 (M4, Report, Confidential)	None	-	Word/PDF files (DOCX/PDF)

Task	Title Task	Responsible Partner(s)	Outputs (month, type, dissemination level)	Dataset Description & Collection Methods (QL/QT)	Data Utility (objective)	Type of Data & Data Format
T1.7 (M16-36)	Scaling up and continuity	VU	D1.6 (M36, Report, Public)	None	-	Word/PDF files (DOCX/PDF)
			MS22: Training session #4 (M35) MS31: Final learning workshop	Notes and minutes of training, training recordings and transcriptions, photos of training (QL)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ To learn and monitor; ○ To investigate and understand the evolution of the transformative network 	Word files (DOCX), Audio files (MP3/MP4), Image files (JPEG)

Abbreviations: QL = qualitative data, QT = quantitative data. T=Task. M=Month. MS = Milestone.

Deliverables. **D1.1** – Tools and Training guideline for setting up and guiding CoPs **D1.2** – Database of contacts with relevant stakeholders. **D1.3** – Tools and training guideline for identifying showcases and designing roadmaps for R&I breakthroughs. **D1.4** – Tools and training guideline for lab activities. **D1.5** – Process architecture for mutual exchange between CoPs within the FOOD2030 Platform. **D1.6** – Updated and final version of all instruments and tools

Table 2. Overview of the characteristics of data collected/used for WP2 (AIT) - Mapping of trends in food systems and related R&I policy frameworks

WP/Task	Title task	Responsible Partner(s)	Outputs (month, type, dissemination level)	Dataset description & Data Collection Methods (QL/QT)	Data Utility (objective)	Type of Data & Data Format
T2.1 (M1-10)	Analysis of visions, trends, drivers and barriers of the food systems and FNS R&I	AIT	Workshop protocol (M10, internal not for public use)	Stakeholder interviews: recordings and transcriptions (QL) Minutes of workshop (QL)	To be used as input in task 2.1	Audio files (MP3/MP4, N=10), Word files (DOCX/PDF)
			D2.1 (M10, Report, Public)	Desk research (past EU funded projects, scientific and grey literature (policy reports) (QL)	To be used as input in WP4 and input for City Labs (WP6)	Word/PDF file (DOCX, PDF)
T2.2 (M1-10)	Mapping food policies and governance of EU food systems and related R&I	UNIBO	D2.2 (M12, Report, Public)	Desk research and collaboration with SCAR working group	To be used as input for Policy Labs (WP5)	Word/PDF file (DOCX, PDF), Excel files (XLSX)
T2.3 (M1-10)	Mapping performance of EU food systems towards meeting European visions	WEcR	D2.3 (M12, Report, Public)	Data cube presenting SDG Impact indicators, Scenario results for EU28 and selected individual member states	To score the performance of EU food systems, map contributions to European FNS, and underline the urgency for action on future-proofing EU's food systems.	Word file (DOCX/PDF), ZIP file, series of data files (CSV, Comma-Separated Values)

Abbreviations: QL = qualitative data, QT = quantitative data. T=Task. M=Month. MS = Milestone.

Deliverables. **D2.1** – Report on baseline and description of identified trends, drivers and barriers of the food system and R&I. **D2.2** – Report on overview and needs, barriers and enablers for policies and governance of EU food systems and FNS R&I - comparison to global systems.. **D2.3** – Résumé of performance of EU food systems towards European FNS and SDGs.

Table 3. Overview of the characteristics of data collected/used for WP3 (ILSI Europe) – Identification of showcases

WP/Task ¹	Title task	Responsible Partner(s)	Outputs (month, type, dissemination level)	Dataset description & Data Collection Methods (QL/QT)	Data Utility (objective)	Type of Data & Data Format
T3.1 (M3-10)	Gathering information on food systems R&I cases	ILSI	MS9 (M6, Report, Confidential)	Expert group kick-off meeting to identify criteria on how to identify showcases, (minutes of expert meeting)	Criteria for showcase selection	Word/PDF file (DOCX/PDF)
			D3.1 (M10, Report, Confidential)	Report on detailed data set of 100-150 RR&I cases: data collection via Online survey (QT); spread via Consortium (including consortium stakeholder database); WP3 expert group; Policy Labs; City Labs; SCAR; MUFPP; Workshop	To identify recent R&I initiatives to select showcases from	Excel file (XLSX) Word/PDF file (DOCX/PDF)
T3.2 (M9-16)	Selecting best cases in food systems R&I	ILSI	MS16 (M15, Dataset, Confidential)	Selection of 10-15 showcases available, minutes of expert meeting	To have an initial dataset on showcases for assessment	Excel File (XLSX) Word/PDF file (DOCX/PDF)
			D3.2 (M16, Report, Confidential)	Report on selected showcases (incl. criteria)	Assess what makes showcases differ from cases	Excel File (XLSX) Word/PDF file (DOCX/PDF)
T3.3 (M17-24)	Presenting R&I food system showcases and preparing guidelines for best practices	EIT Food	D3.3 (M24, Report, Public)	Catalogue of identified showcases (criteria + impact)	Complete assessment of all case data with assessment for their showcase potential	Excel File (XLSX) Word/PDF file (DOCX/PDF)
T3.4 (M24-36)	Assessing changes in selected R&I showcases – impact monitoring tool	EIT Food	MS30 (M32, Dataset, Public)	Dataset from piloting of impact assessment and policy guidance tool	Dataset for further assessment	Excel File (XLSX) Word/PDF file (DOCX/PDF)
			D3.4 (M32, Report, Public)	Impact assessment and policy guidance tool	Showcase assessment tool to be used for future guidance	Excel File (XLSX) Word/PDF file (DOCX/PDF)

Abbreviations: QL = qualitative data, QT = quantitative data. T=Task. M=Month. MS = Milestone.

Deliverables. D3.1 – Report on detailed data set of 100-150 (R)R&I cases. **D3.2** – Report on selected showcases, including criteria for assessment of R&I cases, and ranking. **D3.3** – Catalogue of identified showcases (criteria + impacts). **D3.4** – Impact assessment and policy guidance tool

Table 4. Overview of the characteristics of data collected/used for WP4 (F4L) – Exploration of roadmaps for R&I breakthroughs

WP/Task ¹	Title task	Responsible Partner(s)	Outputs (month, type, dissemination level)	Dataset description & Methods (QL/QT) ²	Data Utility (objective)	Type of Data & Data Format
T4.1 (M6-12)	Identification of research and innovation breakthroughs	F4L, ILSI	D4.1 (M12, Report, Public) Internal workshop: Exploration of Roadmaps for R&I breakthroughs (M6)	Minutes of the workshop	To identify different perspectives of what breakthroughs are	Word/PDF files (DOCX/PDF)
		AIT	MS11 (M10): Workshops on the identification of potential R&I breakthroughs	Minutes and reports from the workshops	To be integrated into D4.1	Word files (DOCX)
T4.2 (M10-16)	Critical success factors for implementation of breakthroughs	AIT	D4.2 (M16, Report, Public)	None	-	Word/PDF files (DOCX/PDF)
		F4L	MS15 (M14): Workshops on the prioritisation of potential R&I breakthroughs and identification of barriers and incentives	Reports from the workshops	To sketch out routes for the realisation of potential breakthroughs, via the multi-stakeholder platform. To be integrated into D4.2	Word files (DOCX)
T4.3 (M10-16)	Forward outlook towards a food system transformation	WeCR	D4.3(M16, Report, Public)	None	-	Word/PDF files (DOCX/PDF)
		F4L	MS19 (M16): Workshop for discussion of position paper	Report from the workshop	To be considered under D4.3	Word/PDF files (DOCX/PDF)
T4.4 (M28-32)	Appropriate instruments for the identification of R&I breakthroughs for the future	F4L	D4.4(M32, Report, Public)	None	-	Word/PDF files (DOCX/PDF)
		F4L	MS27 (M28): Targeted consultation of the draft set of recommendations	Responses to the public consultation on the draft set of recommendations	To be considered under D4.4	Excel files (XLSX)

Abbreviations: QL = qualitative data, QT = quantitative data. T=Task. M=Month. MS = Milestone.

Deliverables. **D4.1** – Report on inventory of R&I breakthroughs. **D4.2** – Report on key success factors for realisation of breakthroughs. **D4.3** – Position paper on urgency, good practices, and pathways for applications of the RRI concept to food system transformation. **D4.4** – Report on instruments for the identification of R&I breakthroughs for the future.

Table 5. Overview of the characteristics of data collected/used for WP5 (ZON) – Policy coherence and programme alignment

WP/Task ¹	Title task	Responsible Partner(s)	Outputs (month, type, dissemination level)	Dataset description & Methods (QL/QT)	Data Utility (objective)	Type of Data and Data Format
T5.1 (M1-36)	Design and implementation of Policy Labs	ZON and AIT	D1.5 (M34, Report, Public)			
T5.2 (M1-36)	Design and establishment of EU Think Tank	VU	D5.2 (M6, Report, Public) 6 EU Think Tank meetings spread over three years	(observation) Notes and Minutes from the EU Think Tank meetings, as well as EU Think Tank meeting specific reports . (QL)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ To investigate the role of the EU Think Tank as transformative network; ○ To monitor the translation of the project's results to EU level 	Word/PDF files (DOCX/PDF)
T5.3 (M5-32)	Framework to increase impact of research proposals on FNS	INRA	D5.3 (M32, Report, Public)			
T5.4 (M3-32)	Development of practical guides or handbooks	ZON	D5.4 (M30, Report, Public) D5.5 (M32,, Website patents filling, etc., Public)			
Policy Labs	Activities and events of Policy Labs	ZON and Policy Lab coordinators	Extra training Policy Lab coordinators: Systems Awareness (M7) Policy Lab meetings #1 -#4 (M11, M14, M18, M28)	Minutes and event specific reports of the extra training as well as the Policy Lab meetings. (QL)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ To monitor and evaluate to the extent to which visions and theories of change converge in the network (WP8); 	Word/PDF files (DOCX/PDF)

Abbreviations: QL = qualitative data, QT = quantitative data. T=Task. M=Month. MS = Milestone.

Deliverables. **D5.1** – Position paper on lessons learned to adjust D4.3. **D5.2** – Terms of Reference of EU Think Tank. **D5.3** – Guidelines/framework for designing and assessing applications towards impact on FNS. **D5.4** – Internal collaboration. **D5.5** – Practical guide or handbook to support set up (of activities for) a Policy Lab

Table 6. Overview of the characteristics of data collected/used for WP6 (Ecsite) – Building competences on food systems R&I and RRI

WP/Task ¹	Title task	Responsible Partner(s)	Outputs (month, type, dissemination level)	Dataset description & Data Collection Methods (QL/QT) ²	Data Utility (objective)	Type of Data & Data format
T6.1 (M1-6)	Setting up and managing 7 City Labs around Europe	Ecsite	MS4 Establishment of City Labs, M3, feedback from coordinators, not specified	Contact details of coordinators	To facilitate future communication and implementation of activities	PDF file
T6.2 (M6-M10)	Mapping and analysis of existing formats, contents and needs	Ecsite	D6.1 (M10, Report, Public)	None	-	PDF file
T6.3 (M11-13)	Prototyping of activities suitable for primary, secondary, University students	Ecsite		None	-	-
T6.4 (M14-24)	Piloting of the prototypes in schools, science centres and Universities	Ecsite	MS21 Piloting of educational training prototypes, M17, Prototypes are available, n/a	None	-	Audio files (MP3/MP4) Word files (DOCX), Image files (JPEG)
			D6.2 (M24, Report, Public)	None	-	PDF file
T6.5 (M24-36)	Production and implementation of the toolkit and dissemination	Ecsite	MS26 Launch of the Toolkit for Training, M26, toolkit finalised and published, see D6.3	None	-	-
			D6.3 (M26, websites, patents, etc., Public)	None	-	-
T6.1 to 6.5 (M1 to M36)	Activities and events of City Labs	Ecsite and partners, Third Parties hosting City Labs	Submissions by City Labs when and as required by the implementation of WP6 tasks Workshops #1 - #3 (M7, M11, M24)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Event specific reports of workshops #1 - #3 Responses to questionnaires, surveys, prototyping, piloting, implementation and event reports stakeholder data; Potential recordings and transcriptions; photos (QL) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To monitor and evaluate to the extent to which visions and theories of change and required competences and skills converge in the network (WP8); To support WP3 and 4 To develop WP6 deliverables 	Audio files (MP3/MP4), Word files (DOCX), Image files (JPEG)

Abbreviations: QL = qualitative data, QT = quantitative data. T=Task. M=Month. MS = Milestone.

Deliverables

D6.1 – Catalogue on analysis of contents, formats, and needs for trainings. **D6.2** – Report on piloting of educational modules. **D6.3** – Toolkit for use of educational modules

Table 7. Overview of the characteristics of data collected/used for WP7 (EUFIC) – Communication, dissemination and future engagement

Responsible Partner(s)	Outputs (month, type, dissemination level)	Dataset description & Data collection Methods (QL/QT) ²	Data Utility (objective)	Type of Data
EUFIC	D7.1 (M3, Report, Public) D7.2 (M24, Report, Public) D7.3 (M6, Public, Websites, patents filling, etc.) D7.4 (M36, Websites, patents filling, etc., Public) D7.5 (M36, Report, Pulic)	-	-	-

Abbreviations: QL = qualitative data, QT = quantitative data. T=Task. M=Month. MS = Milestone.

Deliverables. **D7.1** – Communication and dissemination plan. **D7.2** – Stakeholder engagement plan. **D7.3** – Project identity and website. **D7.4** – Project leaflet and other materials. **D7.5** – Plan for continued communication with stakeholders

Table 8. Overview of the characteristics of data collected/used for WP8 (HIOA) – Learning for Transformation

WP/Task	Title task	Responsible Partner(s)	Outputs (month, type, dissemination level)	Dataset description & Data collection Methods (QL/QT) ²	Data Utility (objective)	Type of Data
T8.1 (M1-36)	Setting up Dynamic Learning Agenda (DLA)	HIOA	D8.1 (M4, Training guide, Public)	-	-	Word/PDF file (DOCX/PDF)
T8.2 (M3-36)	Monitoring the evolving network	HIOA	D8.2 (M32, Report, Public)	DLA log-sheets from Lab Coordinators via email (QL) Minutes from DLA teleconference sessions (QL) Participatory observation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To learn and monitor; To investigate and understand the evolution of the transformative network. 	Word/PDF files (DOCX/PDF)
T8.3 (M3-36)	Monitoring actor diversity and dynamics	HIOA	D8.2 (M32, Report, Public)	Stakeholder data, to be collected via online surveys using <i>Questback</i> (QT/QL) 'Proof of reach' forms to be filled in by Labs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To learn and monitor; To investigate and understand the evolution of the transformative network. 	Excel files (XLSX), Questback (SAV)
T8.4 (M1-36)	Monitoring emerging visions and theories of change	HIOA	D8.2 (M32, Report, Public)	Minutes from vision workshops and Lab meetings (QL)	To monitor emerging visions and theories of change	Word files (DOCX)
T8.5 (M20-36)	Experiment-to-experiment learning	HIOA	Workshop and connection of Labs for mutual exchange (M24)	Minutes from workshop (QL)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To learn and monitor; To investigate and understand the evolution of the transformative network. 	Word/PDF file (DOCX/PDF)
T8.6 (M24-36)	To develop a corresponding toolbox for future M&E activities	HIOA	Experience sharing workshop to make transdisciplinary dialogue work in the complex landscape of FOOD2030. D8.3 (M35, Toolbox, Public)	Minutes from the workshop	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To learn and monitor; To investigate and understand the evolution of the transformative network. 	Word/PDF file (DOCX/PDF)

Abbreviations: QL = qualitative data, QT = quantitative data. T=Task. M=Month. MS = Milestone.

Deliverables. **D8.1** – Tool and Training guide Dynamic Learning Agenda. **D8.2** – Report on tasks 8.1 – 8.5. **D8.3** – Toolbox for integrated reflexive M&E in R&I development

Table 9. Overview of the characteristics of data collected/used for WP9 (VU) – Project management and coordination

Responsible Partner(s)	Outputs (month, type, dissemination level)	Dataset description & Methods (QL/QT)	Data Utility (objective)	Type of Data & Data Format
VU	D9.1 (ORDP, Public) D9.2 (Report, Public) D9.3 (Report, Public) D9.4 (Report, Public)	-	-	-

Abbreviations: QL = qualitative data, QT = quantitative data. T=Task. M=Month. MS = Milestone.

Deliverables. **D9.1** – Data Management Protocols. **D9.2** – Project Execution Handbook. **D9.3** – Final report on ethical issues. **D9.4** – Report for external evaluator

Table 10. Overview of the characteristics of data collected/used for WP10 (VU) – Ethics requirements

Responsible Partner(s)	Outputs (month, type, dissemination level)	Dataset description & Methods (QL/QT)	Data Utility (objective)	Type of Data & Data Format
VU	D10.1 (Confidential) D10.2 (Confidential)	-	-	-

Abbreviations: QL = qualitative data, QT = quantitative data. T=Task. M=Month. MS = Milestone.

Deliverables. **D10.1** – H – Requirements No. 1. **D10.2** – POPD – Requirement No. 2

4. Data security: storage, archiving, transfer and recovery of data

4.1. Data storage and security

Storage: File sharing platform Edugroepen

To store and share data with other partners, partners of FIT4FOOD2030 make use of file sharing platform **Edugroepen**. The FIT4FOOD2030 main page as well as the WP1 – WP9 sub-pages are accessible for all consortium partners. Specific pages, including “EU Think Tank”, “SAB”, “STAB”, “WP3-Expert group”, “City Lab coordinators”, “Policy Lab coordinators”, “VU” and “DLA” are only accessible for a selection of relevant (consortium) partners.

All data on Edugroepen is encrypted at datacentre level to secure data storage. However, this does not mean that documents uploaded to Edugroepen are automatically encrypted. Therefore, researchers should not leave their computer unprotected. This means, researchers should not only sign out from Edugroepen before leaving the room, they should also **close their browser** (without closing the browser, people might be able to access Edugroepen when clicking on the browser).

Persons who stop being involved in the project will be denied access to data and results on Edugroepen and any other repository as soon as notice has been given to the Coordinator.

Storage: Institutions internal network system and the potential need for encryption

Documents containing personal data – referring to **personal identifiers** – need to be stored at institutions internal network system in a secured way. Depending on the security level of institutions’ internal network systems, these documents need to be **encrypted** (e.g. at the VU the *G-drive* is used as internal network system during the project, which is considered safe enough to store moderate risk data without encryption²). However, if the internal system is not appropriate to store moderate risk data in terms of security, it is necessary to encrypt the data. This can be done by special software. Word and Excel files can be encrypted using a password. Although documents are encrypted, researchers may not leave computers unprotected. Computers should always be locked with a password before leaving the room.

Consortium members should comply with the local legislation of their country regarding the removal of personal data after all data has been generated. For example, in the Netherlands it is **not** allowed to keep and store personal data longer than necessary (art. 5 (1) (e) AVG, see also ["VSNU Gedragscode voor gebruik van persoonsgegevens in wetenschappelijk onderzoek"](#)).

Partners need to make sure their employees take necessary measures to prevent unauthorized access to files which include personal data. These may include, among others, the following:

- The storage of personal data on private notebooks, mobile devices or external hard disks should be prevented.
- Transcripts or voice recordings held outside of the approved systems of the partner must be stored on an encrypted device for temporary storage only. They must be transferred to the systems of the partner and deleted from temporary storage as soon as possible.
- Non-useful copies of data and results need to be destroyed after the project has finished.

²Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam Information Risk Classifications (Nov. 2017).

Document name: 171101_InformationSecurity_Confidentialy Matrix (available upon request)

Survey tools

When using a survey tool within FIT4FOOD2030 (e.g. the survey within WP3), or if free online survey tools are used, *the Terms and Conditions* should be read carefully. The Terms and Conditions should tell the researcher:

- Where the provider stores the data; this should be in Europe;
- If the data will be used for commercial activities.
- If the personal data of your respondents is well protected.

In doubt, the partners are encouraged to consult the Coordinator to check if the service provider they are dealing with is operating in line with the GDPR. In such cases, the VU will consult the legal experts of the VU.

4.2. Data archiving and security

After processing of data during the course of the project, relevant data will in principle be archived safely in repository **Zenodo**³ – and potentially in **partners' own repositories** – at the time of submission of publications ('green' model).

Zenodo is an open and public research data repository funded by the European Commission (via the OpenAire Projects FP7 and Horizon 2020), CERN and the Alfred P. Sloan Foundation.

Data containing personal identifiers, which includes, among others, transcripts, meeting notes and minutes, should not be archived on Zenodo, but should be archived in partners' own network with adequate level of security.

Near the end of the project and before archiving a detailed overview will be created to confirm which data will be archived in Zenodo and which data will be archived in partners' own networks only.

It is recommended to archive text documents in PDF/A format (rather than in MS Word), to guarantee access (in its original form) during the entire archiving period⁴.

4.3. Data transfer and security

As described in 3.1. Types of Data, research data and stakeholder data are treated differently in this project.

Stakeholder data, including personal identifiers, can be transferred among the consortium partners without restrictions. Certain personal identifiers of stakeholders (e.g. name, position and organisation) can be included in the external reports, depending on the consent they provided (please see a Sample Informed Consent Form Training and Learning Sessions in Appendix 3).

Research data, on the other hand, is subject to a number of restrictions for transfer.

As described in article 4.3 of the CA, in case of **research data**, it is **only allowed to transfer pseudonymized data among partners of the consortium**. This means, research data containing personal information – called **personal identifiers** – should be pseudonymized to secure personal information before it is transferred to other partners. Edugroepen main page can be used to transfer

³ <http://about.zenodo.org/infrastructure/>

⁴ *DANS Preferred Methods* – PDF document, available [here](#).

research data, including pseudonymized transcripts or survey results (meaning data without personal identifiers).

As described in the CA, pseudonymisation means: *“the processing of personal data in such a manner that the personal data can no longer be attributed to a specific data subject without the use of additional information, provided that such additional information is kept separately and is subject to technical and organisational measures to ensure that the personal data are not attributed to an identified or identifiable natural person”*.

To pseudonymise data, each participant needs to be given a numerical code to replace identifying information and ensure anonymity. The document containing the personal identifiers and numerical codes (the ‘key’) needs to be stored separately from the document containing the anonymized data.

Nevertheless, if data falls under the definition of ‘stakeholder data’ (see section 3.1. Types of Data), pseudonymisation is not necessary for sharing it within the consortium (see the end of this section).

When personal data that is collected for research purposes (i.e. that is also research data) needs to be transferred, this needs to be processed in accordance with the article 4.2 of the CA:

“Each Party shall ensure that its work on the Project complies fully with all applicable local, government and international laws, regulations and guidelines which are effective during the duration of the Consortium Agreement, including those governing health and safety, data protection, including Directive 95/46/EC on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and its successor Regulation 2016/679 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such personal data or its successor, and any implementation thereof in national law, and where relevant, the use of human subjects and good clinical practice (including national legislation implementing the Parliament’s Directive 2001/20/EC on good clinical practice and its successor Regulation 536/2014 (on clinical trials on medicinal products for human use).

In this regard, each Party shall maintain the confidentiality, in accordance with Article 10 of this Consortium Agreement, of all samples and Personal Data relating to the use of human subjects, which is created or used in the course of the Project. Each Party shall secure all necessary declarations or approvals from or to the relevant research ethics committees and authorities before undertaking any part of the Project requiring declaration or approval and shall, if required, obtain properly signed informed consent and acknowledgement forms from any human subjects or their legal guardians who they will involve in the Project.”

Article 4.3.3. is applicable to the recipient of the personal data:

“The Recipient undertakes that all or part of such Personal Data:

- will only be used for the sole purposes of conducting the Project and only for as long as it is necessary for this purpose, to the exclusion of any other application, in particular for commercial purposes;*
- will not be disclosed, distributed, transferred or licensed to a third party, for any purpose whatsoever, without prior written authorization from the Supplier and in accordance with the authorization/declaration necessary for the transfer;*
- will be used and stored in accordance with the applicable legal and regulatory provisions, as set out in Article 4.2. In particular, the Recipient ensures that it has obtained any necessary authorizations and/or opinions and taken appropriate measures for the storage and use of the concerned Personal Data;*

- *will be returned to the Supplier (or destroyed, at the Supplier's discretion and without any copy being made thereof) in the event of the withdrawal of the consent or the exercise of the opposition right of the person which would be communicated by the Supplier to the Recipient;*
- *will no longer be used and will be returned to the Supplier (or destroyed, at the Supplier's discretion) upon request and/or in the event of the termination of this Consortium Agreement and/or upon the expiry thereof and without any copy being made thereof; and*
- *will be used and stored exclusively on the premises of the Recipient within the performance of the Project and by scientists working on the premises of the Recipient or under its direct responsibility and with the same degree of security that it applies to its own Personal Data”.*

Strategy to transfer personal data, in the context of research data

To transfer the personal identifiers of research data (e.g. keys), the Edugroepen main page cannot be used, since the entire consortium has access to this platform. Therefore, a specific service should be used to transfer personal data. **FileSender** is an open source web-based application to send documents securely. This means it is specifically aimed to transfer sensitive data, including personal data. FileSender includes several installations, including *SURF filesender*, which might be used for a transfer between a Dutch and a non-Dutch consortium partner. With SURF filesender, data will be stored in the Netherlands (at surfnet) during 21 days. However, personal data should be encrypted before sending for extra security. The entire list of FileSender possibilities can be found at “FileSender Documentation”: <https://docs.filesender.org/known-installs>.

Data transfer agreements

In the context of research data, before the transfer of personal data to specific partner(s), a **separate bilateral or multilateral data transfer agreement** specifying the conditions of transfer and processing of personal data by the recipient should be agreed on by the supplier and the recipient data, as described in article 4.3 of the CA. If personal data needs to be transferred, a basic agreement will be developed by the VU (meaning the agreement will be under Dutch Law), which can be used by the partners. Nevertheless, consortium partners should still comply to their countries' local additional legislation (as described in section 2.2) regarding the privacy of personal data.

However, **if data is collected as a collaborative effort between consortium partners, there is no need for a separate bilateral or multilateral data transfer agreement.** An example includes the survey of WP2, WP3 and WP4, which is a collaborative effort between ILSI Europe, AIT and F4L. For security reasons during the transfer, pseudonymization is still necessary and personal data (the keys) still needs to be sent separately and securely to the other consortium partner(s) (using Filesender, or a specific Edugroepen subpage only accessible for the specific consortium partners).

If data is collected as a collaborative effort between consortium partners including a Dutch partner, it is not necessary but highly recommended - according to Dutch Law - to have a separate bilateral or multilateral agreement for the transfer of personal data. This agreement will be developed by the VU.

4.4. Data recovery

All consortium partners should use data storage facilities that allow for data recovery (e.g. at the VU, regular back-ups are made of the G-drive). Such data recovering strategies should be checked in advance.

5. FAIR Data

5.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

In order to ensure that the data produced by FIT4FOOD2030 will be accurately cited and retrievable in the future, data produced and used will be discoverable with metadata.

As FIT4FOOD2030 will use Zenodo as repository, metadata standards of Zenodo will be used to make data findable. Zenodo uses *JSON Schema* as internal representation of metadata. It also offers export to other popular formats such as *Dublin Core* or *MARCXML*. The VU will monitor if more specific metadata standards become available during the coming three years which potentially might be used to increase findability of data.

Since data will be collected by different beneficiaries, consortium members might also upload data at local and public repositories of their institution, leading to additional metadata records.

Besides, datasets uploaded to Zenodo will receive a DOI, so that the dataset will always be findable.

To enhance findability and visibility and if possible, references will be included to the datasets in the Research Information System (e.g. for the VU this is PURE. Publications registered in PURE are publicly accessible through the national Narcis archive which is fully accessible via Google (Scholar)⁵).

5.2. Making data openly accessible

Openly available and closed data

The FIT4FOOD2030 project participates in the open access to research data pilot of article 29.3 of the model Grant Agreement (GA). This means all research data will be made openly available after removal of personal identifiers (anonymization). Research data that will be openly shared may include, for example, coding trees generated during qualitative analysis of interview transcripts, meeting notes and materials produced during meetings and anonymized responses to the surveys that were subject to quantitative analysis.

Personal data, meaning data including personal identifiers such as personal information of interviewed participants or survey respondents (and the “keys” used for pseudonymisation), will not be made publicly available. This means, documents containing personal data will not be uploaded on Zenodo, but will be kept in a safe way at the local repository of the partner(s) that collected the data.

Access to data

All partners have the responsibility to share their results with the WP leader and the EB, in order to keep them updated about potential interesting findings to disseminate. Additionally, all partners have the obligation, hence the allocation of resources to do so, to support the dissemination and communication efforts that will have an impact on the project as a whole. The General Assembly (GA) functions as the internal advisory body on issues related to dissemination and exploitation, and (un) solicited external advice will be provided by the independent external Advisory Boards. Results will be shared and made openly accessible via:

1. Open Access journals

Data should be disseminated through the submission to leading Open Access (if possible) scientific journals with broad dissemination. The partners of FIT4FOOD2030 will disseminate the results as

⁵ PURE: <https://www.ub.vu.nl/en/education-research/open-access/uploading-publications/index.aspx>

swiftly as possible, but only after all other partners have been informed about the intention to disseminate as well as the content of the dissemination and have been given a reasonable timeframe in which they can object to (elements of) the intended dissemination. The time frame defined by the CA is **45 calendar days** before the publication. This process will be supported by FIT4FOOD2030's internal platform (Edugroepen).

Each partner will ensure open access to all publications relating to its results, free of charge. At a minimum, each partner makes publications and datasets without personal identifiers available by archiving it in Zenodo, at the time of submission of the publication ('green' model). Additionally, the publications and datasets might be archived in an institution-based repository.

If access cannot be granted, each partner will ensure open access to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results, free of charge.

2. High level debates and scientific sessions

Besides submission of articles to scientific journals, high-level debates and scientific sessions will be organised, to (1) disseminate project outcomes and (2) engage relevant stakeholders in the learning network with a long-term perspective. Moreover, knowledge outputs will be transferred to potential multiplier organisations through meetings and conferences organised or attended by the involved research programming partners.

3. Dissemination materials and website

Furthermore, a project [website](#) is being developed and will be maintained. All project deliverables with a dissemination level 'Public' will be made available without restrictions in the project website. Dissemination materials include project leaflets, press releases, articles in EUFIC's multi-lingual Food Today newsletter, E-newsletters, articles for popular magazines, audio-visual materials, sections on partner websites and social media.

4. Conference

Finally, a concluding conference will be organised (by WP7, EUFIC) at the end of the project in Brussels to present the results to key target audiences: EC officers, opinion leaders/regulators, food manufacturers associations (including SMEs), retailers, consumer organisations, the media and the scientific community.

5.3. Making data interoperable

FIT4FOOD2030 will use the metadata standards of Zenodo and of partners' institutions.

Use of standard vocabulary for all data types is not applicable to FIT4FOOD2030. However, once the form of the data to be archived will take shape, there will be looked into metadata standards presented at the [Digital Curation Centre \(DCC\)](#) to see if there are any useful metadata standards that can be applied to (parts of) the datasets.

5.4. Increase data re-use

The FIT4FOOD2030 consortium will take measures to make it possible for third parties to access, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate data. If such access cannot be granted, each partner will aim to ensure open access to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results, free of charge. Data access might not be granted to third parties when this would interfere with relevant data protection legislations in the countries participating in this project and any applicable EU legislation regarding data protection.

Consortium partners will decide if a license (e.g. CC BY, CC BY-SA) needs to be put to the dataset before publication⁶.

Data-access will be preserved and maintained for a **minimum of 10 years** (which is the minimum period of archiving at VU Amsterdam) after the project has finished and after the moment of publication.

6. Allocation of resources

6.1. Costs for making data FAIR and for long term preservation

Costs for making data fair are estimated to be zero. As described before, Zenodo is funded by the EU, which means archiving data in this repository will be free of charge.

However, repositories of specific institutions will not be free. At the VU, for example, *ArchStor* may potentially be used to archive data, which is 0,22 euro per GB per year.

Consortium partners will use their own budgets to archive personal data in their own repositories.

6.2. Responsibilities for data management

WP9 on project management and coordination is led by the VU. As such, the VU is responsible for providing guidance on data management. However, as described in article 4.2. (see above), consortium partners have the responsibility to make sure their activities are in line with all applicable local, government and international laws, regulations and guidelines (referring to the GDPR and the additional local legislation of the specific country).

7. Ethical aspects

All researchers must obtain **informed consent** from the subjects of their study prior to performing the research itself, being it an interview, questionnaire, focus group, etc., for data sharing and long-term preservation. The informed consent form includes a section on the collection and storage of personal data in databases, a statement regarding the period of storage of data and possible use for future research. Furthermore, participants will be informed that they, or their legal representative, may request data to be deleted when this data has not already been used in publications or presentations. Hard copy informed consent forms should be scanned and encrypted before storing the forms on the institutions internal system. Hard copy forms should be stored in a locked file cabinet.

The VU will provide the informed consent forms as part of WP10 (Ethics requirements) at M12. Deliverable 10.1 will provide detailed information on the informed consent procedures that will be implemented for the participation of humans. Deliverable 10.2 will provide detailed information on the procedures that will be implemented for data collection, storage, protection, retention and destruction and confirmation that these procedures will comply with the national as well as the EU legislation.

The above also means that participants of the four Training and Learning sessions organised within WP1, Workshops organised within WP3 and WP4, and Workshops organised by Policy and City Lab

⁶ <http://www.dcc.ac.uk/resources/how-guides/license-research-data>

coordinators, need to sign an informed consent form (Appendix 3). Furthermore, people participating in these trainings and workshops need to sign a **media release form**, since data might be shared with WP7 for communication and dissemination purposes (Appendix 4).

Appendix 1. Template Horizon 2020 DMP

The table below provides a summary of the Data Management Plan (DMP) issues to be addressed according to the template Horizon 2020 DMP.⁷

DMP component	Issues to be addressed
1. Data summary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ State the purpose of the data collection/generation ○ Explain the relation to the objectives of the project ○ Specify the types and formats of data generated/collected ○ Specify if existing data is being re-used (if any) ○ Specify the origin of the data ○ State the expected size of the data (if known) ○ Outline the data utility: to whom will it be useful
2. FAIR Data 2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Outline the discoverability of data (metadata provision) ○ Outline the identifiability of data and refer to standard identification mechanism. Do you make use of persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers? ○ Outline naming conventions used ○ Outline the approach towards search keyword ○ Outline the approach for clear versioning ○ Specify standards for metadata creation (if any). If there are no standards in your discipline describe what type of metadata will be created and how
2.2 Making data openly accessible	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Specify which data will be made openly available? If some data is kept closed provide rationale for doing so ○ Specify how the data will be made available ○ Specify what methods or software tools are needed to access the data? Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included? Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)? ○ Specify where the data and associated metadata, documentation and code are deposited ○ Specify how access will be provided in case there are any restrictions
2.3. Making data interoperable	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Assess the interoperability of your data. Specify what data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies you will follow to facilitate interoperability. ○ Specify whether you will be using standard vocabulary for all data types present in your data set, to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability? If not, will you provide mapping to more commonly used ontologies?
2.4. Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Specify how the data will be licenced to permit the widest reuse possible ○ Specify when the data will be made available for re-use. If applicable, specify why and for what period a data embargo is needed ○ Specify whether the data produced and/or used in the project is useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why ○ Describe data quality assurance processes

⁷ H2020 Programme. Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020.
http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Specify the length of time for which the data will remain re-usable
3. Allocation of resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Estimate the costs for making your data FAIR. Describe how you intend to cover these costs ○ Clearly identify responsibilities for data management in your project ○ Describe costs and potential value of long term preservation
4. Data security	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Address data recovery as well as secure storage and transfer of sensitive data
5. Ethical aspects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ To be covered in the context of the ethics review, ethics section of DoA and ethics deliverables. Include references and related technical aspects if not covered by the former
6. Other	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Refer to other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management that you are using (if any)

Appendix 2. Publication Plan

At the end of **May 2018**, all work package leaders will send their first draft publication plan to the Coordinator (VU), including answers to the following questions:

- *On which activities or work package tasks would you like to publish?*
- *What types of publication do you plan for? E.g. ‘white literature’: research article, literature review, book chapter etc. , or ‘grey literature’: reports, policy briefs, etc.*
- *What is the planned timeline for submission (year and perhaps quarter)?*
- *Among the members of your work package, who will work on the publication? What do you plan regarding authorship?*
- *Who can be the target publisher and/or audience of your publications?*

The draft publication plans will be discussed during the Executive Board meeting **early July**.

The final and overall publication plan will be ready in **September 2018**.

Appendix 3. Sample Informed Consent Form Training and Learning Sessions

FIT4FOOD2030
De Boelelaan 1105
1081 HV AMSTERDAM

Permission to Use Audio and/or Video Recordings

Name: _____

Location: Lab Coordinators Training, Amsterdam

During the lab coordinators training, you may be recorded on audio and/or videotape so that your information may be used for research within the project. You have three choices regarding the audiotape, videotape, and/or transcript of the interview. The materials may be designated either **“public,” “for research only,”** or **“private.”**

If you designate the materials **“public,”** your audiotape(s) or videotape(s), FIT4FOOD2030 may use the materials from the training for future research and your materials will remain part of its permanent collection.

If you designate the materials **“for research only,”** your audiotape(s) or videotape(s) will be analyzed by researchers and your information will be used in studies. Your information will be reported in a way that does not identify you and your materials will be destroyed after the study is complete.

If you designate the materials **“private,”** the audiotape(s) or videotape(s) will never be released by FIT4FOOD2030. The only records of the interview will belong solely to you.

If in the future you wish to change the status of your audiotape(s), videotape(s), and/or transcript(s), you may contact the FIT4FOOD2030:

___ I hereby designate the materials as **public** and give permission for my audiotape(s) or videotape(s) to be used by FIT4FOOD2030.

___ I hereby designate the audiotape(s) or videotape(s) **for research only** and give my permission for researchers to use my materials as part of the research study. I want my materials to be reported so that they will not identify me and destroyed when the study is complete.

___ I hereby designate these materials as **private** and do NOT give my permission for my audiotape(s) or videotape(s) to be used by FIT4FOOD2030. The materials will be given to you for your own private use.

Printed name _____

Organization Name (if applicable) _____

Date _____

Signature _____

Appendix 4. Sample Media Release Form Training and Learning sessions

FIT4FOOD2030
De Boelelaan 1105
1081 HV AMSTERDAM

Permission to Use Photographs and/or Videos

Name: _____

Location: Lab Coordinators Training, Amsterdam

I grant to FIT4FOOD2030, its representatives and employees the right to take photographs of me and my property in connection with the above-identified subject. I authorize FIT4FOOD2030, its assigns and transferees to copyright, use and publish the same in print and/or electronically. I agree that FIT4FOOD2030 may use such photographs of me with or without my name and for any lawful purpose, including for example such purposes as publicity, illustration, advertising, and Web content.

I have read and understand the above:

Printed name _____

Organization Name (if applicable) _____

Date _____

Signature _____